

Euclid's reductio reduced

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Let $\{p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_n\}$ be the first n primes. Then the product

$$q_1 = p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_n$$

is even - so not a new prime - and let

$$q_2 = q_1/2$$

Then q_2 is obviously odd - being the product of odd primes - so

$$q_3 = q_2 + 1$$

is even, hence also not a new prime; let now

$$q_4 = q_3/2$$

If q_4 is odd it may or may not be a prime, new or not; if it is even then

$$q_4/2$$

may be even or odd, and again primality is either false or inconclusive.

The moral here is that Euclid's reductio argument for the infinitude of primes cannot exclude the prime 2 in the starting list; but the prime set is infinite anyway, with or without 2, isn't it?